

INFLUENCE OF ECO-LABELLING ON BRAND LOYALTY AMONG ENVIRONMENTALLY CONSCIOUS CONSUMERS IN AWKA METROPOLIS, ANAMBRA STATE

Ifeanyichukwu Nwadiogo Oranusi (Ph.D)

Department of Marketing, Faculty of management Science, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.

E-mail: in.oranusi@unizik.edu.ng

ORCID ID: 0009-0000-7277-6439

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Abstract: *The growing global concern for environmental sustainability has positioned eco-labelling as a crucial method for encouraging sustainable consumer behaviour, particularly in emerging markets like Nigeria. The study aimed to examine the influence of eco-labelling on brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis, Anambra State, Nigeria. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The correlational survey research design was adopted for the study. Data were collected from 400 environmentally conscious consumers through a structured questionnaire and analyzed using simple regression analysis. The findings reveal that consumer awareness of eco-labels and perceived credibility of eco-labels have strong positive influence on brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis. Findings further revealed that consumer awareness of eco-labels and perceived credibility of eco-labels have significant positive influence on brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis. The study recommended among others that the Anambra State Ministry of Commerce and Industry, in collaboration with relevant agencies, should initiate and sponsor public campaigns to raise awareness about eco-labels and their importance in promoting sustainable consumption. It was also recommended that businesses operating in Awka Metropolis should conduct workshops and community outreach programmes to educate consumers about eco-labels.*

Introduction

Environmental concerns and the rising cases of global warming have heightened the need for adopting environmentally conscious practices in the business environment. Businesses are expected to promote innovative marketing

practices that foster environmental sustainability. One of such practice is eco-labelling. Eco-labelling serves as more than just a marketing tool. The international emphasis on sustainable consumption, as highlighted in the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals,

particularly Goal 12: Responsible Consumption and Production, places eco-labelling at the forefront of strategies aimed at encouraging environmentally responsible behaviour.

Eco-labelling or environmental product labelling is a signal of a brand's commitment to environmental stewardship, resonating deeply with consumers who align their purchasing decisions with their values. Research highlights that eco-labels enhance consumer trust by providing transparent information about a product's environmental impact (Thøgersen et al., 2017). Taufique et al. (2019) opined that eco-labelling informs consumers about a product's influence on the environment. Miranda-Ackerman and Azzaro-Pantel (2017) defined the process of measuring a product's carbon footprint, water use and social responsibility using a label or certification. According to Taufique et al. (2019), eco-labels offer consumers reliable and consistent information about a product's environmental impact. Abel and Anyakaoha (2024) saw eco-labelling as a voluntary tool that communicates the environmental performance of products through standardized labels, fostering trust and sustainable consumption. Delmas and Lessmann (2017) further defined eco-labelling as "a market-driven approach that provides consumers with credible information about a product's environmental attributes, encouraging greener purchasing behaviors.

The rising cases of global warming, evidenced by increasing temperatures, extreme weather events and melting ice caps, have amplified the need for businesses to adopt practices that

mitigate environmental harm. Consumers are now more aware of their ecological footprint, seeking products that align with their values of sustainability and responsibility (Thøgersen et al., 2017). Eco-labels serve as a critical signal of a brand's commitment to these values, providing transparency about a product's environmental influence and fostering trust among consumers (Taufique et al., 2019). In Nigeria, where rapid urbanization and growing consumer markets are driving demand for sustainable goods, eco-labelling offers businesses a way to differentiate themselves in competitive sectors like food, cosmetics and household products (Ogunleye & Adebayo, 2021). However, the effectiveness of eco-labels hinges on consumer awareness, trust in certification processes and the perceived authenticity of environmental claims, particularly in markets like Awka where economic and cultural factors shape purchasing decisions.

Brand loyalty is a fundamental concept in consumer behaviour. Brand loyalty refers to the tendency of consumers to favour a particular brand repeatedly due to trust and shared principles (Kotler & Keller, 2016). According to Aaker and Joachimsthaler (2018), brand loyalty reflects a customer's level of attachment to a brand, demonstrated by a willingness to repurchase despite changes in circumstances or marketing efforts by competitors. Oliver (2019) similarly viewed brand loyalty as a strong and enduring intention to consistently choose a preferred product or service, resulting in repeated purchases. Chaudhuri and Holbrook (2015) added that brand loyalty includes two

dimensions: attitudinal loyalty, based on emotional attachment and behavioural loyalty, represented by repeated buying actions. For consumers who prioritise sustainability, brand loyalty is often influenced by ethical and environmental considerations in addition to product performance and pricing. Eco-labels serve a pivotal function in this context by communicating a brand's commitment to environmental responsibility, thereby fostering deeper emotional ties and promoting customer retention (Chen & Chang, 2018).

Studies have shown that eco-labels not only appeal to eco-conscious buyers but also increase their willingness to pay higher prices for certified goods, reinforcing brand allegiance (D'Souza et al., 2015). In Nigeria, both public policy frameworks and private sector efforts are increasingly supporting sustainable production practices, with eco-labels becoming more common in sectors such as agriculture and fast-moving consumer goods (FMCGs) (Ogunleye & Adebayo, 2021). Nevertheless, the effectiveness of these efforts hinges on their alignment with the beliefs, preferences and awareness levels of local consumers. While globally recognised labels like Fairtrade or USDA Organic are familiar to international audiences, their significance in places like Awka may be shaped by local knowledge and cultural interpretations of sustainability (Taufique et al., 2019). This research therefore seeks to investigate how eco-labelling influences brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis, Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

The rising threat of global warming and environmental degradation has heightened consumer awareness of sustainability, driving demand for environmentally friendly products in markets worldwide, including Nigeria. Awka is a fast growing urban city with an increasing number of environmentally conscious consumers. These consumers search for products that align with their values of ecological responsibility. Eco-labelling, which certifies products as environmentally sustainable, has emerged as an important strategy for businesses to appeal to these consumers. However, despite the growing adoption of eco-labels in industries such as food, cosmetics and household goods, there is limited understanding of how these labels influence brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka. Challenges such as low awareness of eco-labels, skepticism about certification credibility and economic constraints that prioritize affordability over sustainability may undermine the effectiveness of eco-labelling in fostering long-term consumer loyalty (Adebayo & Iweala, 2020; Taufique et al., 2019).

The problem of this study lies in the uncertainty surrounding the extent to which eco-labelling influences brand loyalty in the context of Awka Metropolis, where cultural, economic and social factors shape consumer behavior. While eco-labels are designed to build trust and encourage repeat purchases by signaling a brand's commitment to sustainability (Thøgersen et al., 2017), their influence in a developing market like Awka remains underexplored. Without a clear

understanding of how eco-labels affect consumer trust, preference and loyalty, businesses may struggle to effectively leverage eco-labelling to differentiate themselves in a competitive market. This study seeks to address this gap by investigating the influence of eco-labelling on brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis, Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to examine the influence of eco-labelling on brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis, Anambra State. Specifically, the study ascertained the influence of:

1. Consumer awareness of eco-labels on brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis.
2. Influence of perceived credibility of eco-labels on brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the influence of consumer awareness of eco-labels on brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis?
2. What is the influence of perceived credibility of eco-labels on brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis?

Null Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant positive relationship between consumer awareness of

eco-labels and brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis.

2. Perceived credibility of eco-labels does not significantly influence brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis.

Literature Review

Taufique et al. (2019) investigated consumer understanding and perception of eco-labels, emphasizing their role in shaping environmentally conscious purchasing decisions. Conducted in Malaysia with a survey of 500 consumers and structural equation modeling, their study found that consumer awareness and trust in eco-labels significantly influence purchase intentions, which in turn foster brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers. The researchers highlighted that clear, credible eco-labels enhance consumer confidence in a brand's sustainability claims, leading to repeated purchases. This focus on awareness as a driver of loyalty sets the stage for understanding similar dynamics in other developing markets. Building on the importance of awareness, Thøgersen et al. (2017) explored consumer responses to eco-labels in a European context, focusing on their influence on brand trust and loyalty. Using a survey of 1,200 consumers across multiple countries and regression analysis, the study found that eco-labels positively affect brand loyalty by signaling a brand's commitment to environmental sustainability. The researchers noted that consumers with high environmental consciousness are more likely to develop

attitudinal and behavioral loyalty toward eco-labelled brands, though skepticism about label authenticity can hinder these effects. This finding connects to the need for credible certifications, a theme further explored in Nigerian contexts.

In a similar vein, Adebayo and Iweala (2020) examined eco-labelling in Nigeria's organic food sector, providing a localized perspective relevant to Awka. Their study, based on a survey of 300 consumers in Lagos and analyzed using descriptive statistics and correlation analysis, found that eco-labels, such as the NAFDAC Green Dot, enhance brand loyalty by increasing perceived product quality and trust. However, low awareness and economic barriers, such as the higher cost of eco-labelled products, limited adoption. This study's emphasis on economic constraints links to broader challenges in developing markets, where affordability often competes with sustainability. Complementing this Nigerian perspective, Panopoulos et al. (2022) investigated eco-labels' influence on consumer purchase decisions in Enugu State, Nigeria, a region geographically close to Awka. Using a sample of 400 young consumers and structural equation modeling, their study found that eco-label credibility significantly enhances brand trust, which mediates the relationship between eco-labels and brand loyalty. The researchers highlighted the role of peer influence and social pressure in amplifying loyalty, particularly among younger consumers. This focus on social dynamics connects to the potential for community-driven marketing strategies in Awka's bustling markets like Eke

Awka. Expanding on the role of eco-labels in emerging markets, Waris et al. (2021) studied the purchase of energy-efficient appliances in Pakistan, a context with economic and cultural similarities to Nigeria. Their survey of 310 households, analyzed using partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM), revealed that eco-labels, particularly energy-saving labels, significantly influence purchase intentions and brand loyalty. Environmental consciousness and curiosity were identified as key drivers, with clear label communication critical to overcoming skepticism. This emphasis on clear communication ties back to the need for consumer education, a recurring theme across these studies.

Similarly, Akinfenwa et al. (2024) explored eco-labelling's influence on purchase intentions among young consumers in Enugu State, Nigeria, using a survey of 350 respondents and regression analysis. Their findings confirmed that eco-labels, such as those indicating recyclability or organic certification, increase trust and favorable perceptions, leading to higher brand loyalty. The study noted that willingness to pay a premium for eco-labelled products is strong among environmentally conscious consumers, but low awareness remains a barrier. This finding reinforces the need for targeted awareness campaigns in Awka, where similar demographic and economic conditions may limit eco-label adoption.

Methods

The correlational research design was adopted for the study. The study was conducted in Anambra State. The target population comprised

environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis. They comprised adults aged 18 and above who actively consider environmental factors in their purchasing decisions, such as those seeking eco-labelled products in markets like Eke Awka and Nkwo Amenyi. A sample size of 400 consumers was determined using the Taro Yamane formula at a 95% confidence level, selected through purposive sampling to ensure participants demonstrate environmental consciousness, recruited from major markets and retail stores in Awka. Primary data were collected using a structured questionnaire divided into four sections: demographic information (age, gender and occupation) consumer awareness of eco-labels, perceived credibility of eco-labels and brand loyalty, each measured on a 5-point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (UD), Disagree and Strongly Agree (SA). To ensure validity, the questionnaire was reviewed by experts in marketing and consumer behavior and a pilot test with 30 respondents was conducted to refine the instrument. Reliability was tested using Cronbach's Alpha, yielding values of 0.89 for

consumer awareness, 0.76 for perceived credibility and 0.85 for brand loyalty, all exceeding the 0.70 threshold, indicating high reliability (Hair et al., 2019). Out of 400 copies of the instrument administered, 362 copies were returned in good condition and used for the analysis of data. Data were analyzed using simple regression analysis in SPSS version 25 to examine the influence of consumer awareness and perceived credibility (independent variables) on brand loyalty (dependent variable) at a 0.05 level of significance. Regression results interpreted based on beta coefficients, R-squared values and p-values, where a p-value less than 0.05 indicates rejection of the null hypotheses. Ethical considerations were prioritized, with informed consent obtained, confidentiality maintained through unique identifiers and voluntary participation ensured without collecting personal identifying information.

Results

Research Question One: What is the influence of consumer awareness of eco-labels on brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis?

Table 1: Summary of Regression Analysis on the Influence of Consumer Awareness of Eco-Labels on Brand Loyalty among Environmentally Conscious Consumers in Awka Metropolis

	Unstandardized	Std. Dev.	Standardized
	β	β	β
Constant	28.008	10.766	
Consumer Awareness of Eco-Labels	.695	.612	.712
R	.712		
R ²	.583		
Adj. R ²	.574		

The regression analysis in Table 1 shows a strong positive influence of consumer awareness of eco-labels on brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis, as indicated by an R-value of 0.712. This means that consumer awareness of eco-labels has a strong linear relationship with on brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis. The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.583$) indicates that 58.3% of the variation in brand loyalty can be explained by consumer awareness of eco-labels alone. The adjusted R^2 (0.574), which accounts for the number of predictors in the model, still confirms a strong explanatory power. The unstandardized

coefficient ($\beta = 0.695$) suggests that for every one-unit increase in consumer awareness of eco-labels, the level of brand loyalty increases by 0.695 units, holding other factors constant. The standardized coefficient ($\beta = 0.712$) further supports that consumer awareness of eco-labels has a strong influence in predicting brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis, compared to other possible variables not included in the model.

Research Question Two: What is the influence of perceived credibility of eco-labels on brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis?

Table 2: Summary of Regression Analysis on the Influence of Perceived Credibility of Eco-Labels on Brand Loyalty among Environmentally Conscious Consumers in Awka Metropolis

	Unstandardized	Std. Dev.	Standardized
	β	β	β
Constant	40.550	15.220	
Perceived Credibility of Eco-Labels	.745	.718	.830
R	.830		
R^2	.775		
Adj. R^2	.745		

The regression result in Table 2 reveals a very strong influence of perceived credibility of eco-labels on brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers, as indicated by an R-value of 0.830. This suggests that changes in perceived credibility of eco-labels are strongly associated with changes in brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis. The coefficient of determination (R^2

= 0.775) indicates that 77.5% of the variation in brand loyalty is explained by perceived credibility of eco-labels alone. This is a substantial proportion, suggesting that perceived credibility of eco-labels is a major factor influencing brand loyalty in the studied population. The adjusted R^2 of 0.745 further confirms the model's strength, even after correcting for potential overfitting. The

unstandardized coefficient ($\beta = 0.745$) shows that for every one-unit increase in perceived credibility of eco-labels, the level of brand loyalty increases by 0.745 units. The standardized beta coefficient ($\beta = 0.830$) emphasizes that

perceived credibility of eco-labels is a very strong predictor of brand loyalty.

Null Hypothesis One: There is no significant positive influence of consumer awareness of eco-labels on brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis.

Table 3: Test of Significance of Simple Regression Analysis on the Influence of Consumer Awareness of Eco-Labels on Brand Loyalty among Environmentally Conscious Consumers in Awka Metropolis

	Unstandardized β	Std. Dev. β	Standardized β	t-value	p-value
Constant	28.008	10.766		12.060	0.000
Consumer Awareness of Eco-Labels	0.695	0.612	0.712	18.755	0.000
R	0.712				
R ²	0.583				
Adj. R ²	0.574				
F	44.127				0.000

Table 3 showed that the t-value of 18.755 for the domestic violence predictor and the p-value of 0.000 (which is less than 0.05) indicate that the effect of consumer awareness of eco-labels on brand loyalty is statistically significant. Similarly, the F-value of 44.127 with a p-value of 0.000 confirms that the overall regression model is significant. The researcher therefore rejects

the null hypothesis. Thus, consumer awareness of eco-labels significantly brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis.

Null Hypothesis Two: Perceived credibility of eco-labels does not significantly influence brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis.

Table 4: Test of Significance of Simple Regression Analysis on Influence of Perceived Credibility of Eco-Labels on Brand Loyalty among Environmentally Conscious Consumers in Awka Metropolis

	Unstandardized β	Std. Dev. β	Standardized β	t-value	p-value
Constant	40.550	15.220		20.043	0.000
Perceived Credibility of Eco-Labels	0.745	0.718	0.830	36.705	0.000

R	0.830	
R ²	0.775	
Adj. R ²	0.745	
F	58.354	0.000

Data in Table 4 shows a very strong and statistically significant influence of perceived credibility of eco-labels on brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis. The correlation coefficient ($R = 0.830$) indicates a strong positive association. The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.775$) suggests that 77.5% of the variation in brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis is explained by perceived credibility of eco-labels. The adjusted R^2 (0.745) further supports the robustness of the model. The t-value for perceived credibility of eco-labels is 36.705, with a p-value of 0.000, indicating a highly significant effect. The F-value of 58.354, also with a p-value of 0.000, confirms that the overall regression model is significant. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, perceived credibility of eco-labels is a significantly influence brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis.

Discussion

The findings of the study revealed that consumer awareness of eco-labels has a strong positive influence on brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis. This finding may have resulted because awareness of eco-labels empowers consumers to make informed purchasing decisions that align with their environmental

values, thereby fostering trust and emotional attachment to brands that demonstrate sustainability commitments. When consumers are knowledgeable about eco-labels, such as those indicating organic production or reduced carbon footprints, they perceive these brands as authentic and reliable, which strengthens their loyalty through repeated purchases. This awareness enhances the perceived value of eco-labelled products, encouraging consumers to prioritize brands that reflect their environmental concerns over competitors. This finding is in agreement with Taufique et al. (2019), who established a direct link between consumer understanding of eco-labels and increased purchase intentions, leading to brand loyalty in developing markets. Their study highlighted that awareness enhances consumer confidence in eco-labels, which translates into stronger brand commitment. Additionally, Thøgersen et al. (2017) found that consumer awareness of eco-labels significantly boosts brand trust, which in turn fosters loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers. They noted that informed consumers are more likely to perceive eco-labelled brands as credible, reducing skepticism and encouraging long-term loyalty. Similarly, Adebayo and Iweala (2020) reported that awareness of eco-labels, such as Nigeria's NAFDAC Green Dot, enhances perceived

product quality and trust, leading to stronger brand loyalty in the Nigerian context.

Furthermore, the study found that consumer awareness of eco-labels significantly influences brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis. This significant relationship suggests that well-informed consumers are more likely to develop both attitudinal loyalty (emotional connection to the brand) and behavioral loyalty (consistent repurchasing) when they recognize and understand eco-labels. The visibility and clarity of eco-labels in markets like Eke Awka and Nkwo Amenyi likely play a crucial role in reinforcing consumer trust, as these labels serve as tangible proof of a brand's environmental responsibility. This is in agreement with Panopoulos et al. (2022) who reported that consumer awareness of eco-labels is an important driver of brand loyalty in Nigeria, particularly among young consumers who value sustainability. This notion is supported by the current study's findings, where environmentally conscious consumers in Awka view eco-labels as a signal of a brand's alignment with their values, fostering loyalty. This is in line with Akinfenwa et al. (2024) who found that awareness of eco-labels significantly increases trust and purchase intentions among young Nigerian consumers, leading to sustained brand loyalty.

The findings of the study also revealed that perceived credibility of eco-labels has a strong positive influence on brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis. This finding may have resulted because credible eco-labels serve as a reliable

signal of a brand's commitment to environmental sustainability, fostering trust and confidence among consumers. When eco-labels are perceived as authentic and backed by trustworthy certification processes, environmentally conscious consumers in Awka are more likely to develop an emotional connection with the brand, leading to sustained loyalty. This credibility reduces skepticism and enhances the perceived value of eco-labelled products, encouraging consumers to consistently choose these brands over others. This finding aligns with Panopoulos et al. (2022), who found that eco-label credibility significantly enhances brand trust, which mediates the relationship between eco-labels and brand loyalty among young consumers in Nigeria's Enugu State, near Awka. This suggests that credible eco-labels, perceived as transparent and verifiable, foster stronger consumer loyalty by reinforcing trust in a brand's sustainability claims. Similarly, Akinfenwa et al. (2024) reported that the perceived credibility of eco-labels, such as those indicating recyclability or organic certification, significantly increases trust and favorable perceptions, leading to higher brand loyalty among young Nigerian consumers.

Furthermore, the findings of the study showed that perceived credibility of eco-labels significantly influences brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis. This significant relationship suggests that trust in the authenticity of eco-labels directly strengthens both attitudinal loyalty (emotional attachment) and behavioral loyalty (repeat purchases) in markets. This is in

tandem with Waris et al. (2021) who found that credible eco-labels, particularly those related to energy efficiency, significantly influence brand loyalty in emerging markets by enhancing consumer trust and reducing skepticism. Waris et al. (2021) further concluded that perceived credibility of eco-labels has a significant effect on brand loyalty.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher concludes that eco-labelling significantly influence brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis, Anambra State. Findings showed that consumer awareness of eco-labels has a strong positive influence on brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis. Furthermore, the perceived credibility of eco-labels has a strong positive influence on brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka Metropolis. It is, therefore, crucial for businesses in Awka Metropolis to prioritize consumer education and credible eco-labelling practices to foster sustained brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. The Anambra State Ministry of Commerce and Industry, in collaboration with relevant agencies, should initiate and sponsor public campaigns to raise awareness about eco-labels and their importance in promoting sustainable

consumption. These campaigns should educate consumers about the meaning and benefits of eco-labels, as well as how to identify credible certifications, to enhance trust and encourage loyalty to eco-labelled brands.

2. Businesses operating in Awka Metropolis should conduct workshops and community outreach programmes to educate consumers about eco-labels? These programmes should focus on explaining the environmental benefits of eco-labelled products and how they align with sustainability goals, fostering greater awareness and encouraging repeat purchases among environmentally conscious consumers.

3. The Anambra State government and trade associations should establish verification systems to ensure the credibility of eco-labels used by businesses. This could include partnerships with recognized certification bodies to provide transparent and trustworthy eco-labels, reducing consumer skepticism and enhancing brand loyalty in the competitive markets in Awka metropolis..

4. Business associations and marketing boards should integrate eco-labelling education into their training programmes for local businesses and marketers. These programmes should equip businesses with strategies to effectively communicate the value of eco-labels to consumers, emphasizing transparency and authenticity to build trust and foster long-term brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers.

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